

A Multi-modal Hierarchical Approach for Chinese Spelling Correction Using Multi-Head Attention and Residual Connections^①

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Abstract

The primary objective of Chinese Spelling Correction is to detect and correct erroneous characters within Chinese text, which can result from various factors, such as inaccuracies in pinyin representation, character resemblance, and semantic discrepancies. However, existing methods often struggle to fully address these types of errors, impacting the overall correction accuracy. This paper introduces a multi-modal feature encoder designed to efficiently extract features from three distinct modalities: pinyin, semantics, and character morphology. Unlike previous methods that rely on direct fusion or fixed-weight summation to integrate multi-modal information, our approach employs a multi-head attention mechanism to focus more on relevant modal information while disregarding less pertinent data. To prevent issues such as gradient explosion or vanishing, the model incorporates a residual connection of the original text vector for fine-tuning. This approach ensures robust model performance by maintaining essential linguistic details throughout the correction process. Experimental evaluations on the SIGHAN benchmark dataset demonstrate that our model outperforms baseline approaches across various metrics and datasets, confirming its effectiveness and feasibility.

Key words: Chinese Spelling Correction; Multiple-headed attention; Multi-modal fusion; Residual Connection; Pinyin encoder

0 Introduction

In the current era marked by a data explosion, the use of the Chinese language is increasingly widespread. Accordingly, there is a growing demand for Chinese text error correction in industries that handle large volumes of text. This demand is driven by two primary challenges: the high error rate in manual text input and the substantial time and cost associated with manual proofreading. In response to these challenges, Chinese text error correction has emerged as a significant research issue within the field of natural language processing. Compared to English, Chinese text

correction is more challenging due to the language's complexity and ambiguity. In recent years, this area has become a prominent research topic in the field of natural language processing.

The development of Chinese text error correction technology dates back to the 1980s, initially utilizing rule-based and statistical methods. However, these early approaches could only correct specific typos and were ineffective for other types of errors, such as missing characters, redundant characters, and various other mistakes. With the advancement of deep learning technology, neural network-based methods

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for Chinese text error correction have gradually become mainstream. By training on large-scale corpora, deep learning models can learn high-level features, making them more adept at handling the complexity and ambiguity of the Chinese language.

Chinese spelling errors are particularly important compared to other types of text errors. Due to the nature of the language, where many characters share similar sounds or visual components, these errors frequently occur in both writing and digital input. The speed and convenience of typing often exacerbate spelling errors. Such errors can significantly alter the meaning of a sentence, sometimes resulting in misunderstandings or confusion. For example, confusing the characters for "吃" (chī, meaning "eat") and "持" (chí, meaning "hold") can change the context of a sentence entirely. Accurate spelling is foundational for addressing other types of errors, such as grammar and semantic errors. If spelling errors are not corrected, they can complicate the identification and correction of these other issues, as they may obscure the intended meaning or structure of the text. Thus, Chinese spelling errors are a crucial aspect of text quality, with significant implications for communication clarity, comprehension, and the effectiveness of other text correction processes.

Chinese spelling errors are primarily categorized into two types: pinyin errors, caused by similar-sounding phonetics, and glyph errors, resulting from visually similar characters. About 83% of the errors are due to pinyin similarities, while 48% result from glyph similarities^[1]. In the example in Table 1, the first case is that "犯" and "饭" are pronounced the same way, and the second case is that "字" and "学" are similar in shape. Despite advancement, current models often tend to ignore the important relationship between different modal information during integration, and sometimes they neglect pronunciation or glyph information. FASpell^[2] uses a denoising auto-encoder based on BERT(Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers)^[3] to generate candidate characters using minimal annotated data. Although this model simplifies the correction process, it is limited to simple misspelling scenarios and is not effective for complex scenarios. Liu et al.^[4] proposed a pretrained masked language model that incorporates speech information and uses a modified confusion set

instead of a prediction mask. However, this approach weights all modal information equally, which ignores the differences and relative importance of each modality. Consequently, the challenge lies in effectively fusing the various modalities to enhance the model's performance.

Table1 Examples of Chinese spelling mistakes, with the misspelled characters highlighted in red, and the corresponding phonics are given in brackets

Type	Sentence	correction
Pinyin errors	我去吃犯(fan4)了	饭(fan4)
Glyph errors	好好字(zi4)习	学(xue2)

In this paper, we propose a Chinese spelling error correction approach using three modal features: pinyin, semantic, and glyph information. First, the pinyin sequence of Chinese characters is used for feature extraction, capturing phonetic information. Second, the Transformer^[5] model is employed to extract semantic features, leveraging its capability to understand contextual meanings. Finally, glyph information is obtained by converting each Chinese character into an image and using ResNet^[6] to perform feature extraction, capturing the unique glyph patterns of each character.

To effectively integrate information from the three different modalities, this paper introduces a multi-modal fusion module that utilizes a multi-head attention mechanism. This mechanism dynamically adjusts the weight of each modality, optimizing the use of multi-modal information. Additionally, to preserve the original Chinese character information, residual connection technology is incorporated to refine the model's output, further enhancing the accuracy of the results. Experiments are conducted on the SIGHAN benchmark^[7-9] to assess the performance of the proposed model. Results indicate that our model achieves significant improvements over previous state-of-the-art models. Experiments conducted on the SIGHAN benchmark demonstrate the proposed model's efficacy.

The main contributions of this work are as follows.

(1) The newly developed methodology performs the Chinese Spelling Correction task by utilizing not only the textual semantics but also the pinyin and glyph information of Chinese characters. This ap-

proach provides a more robust and nuanced understanding of the text, thereby enhancing the accuracy of the correction process.

(2) The methodology incorporates a multi-head attention mechanism to enhance multi-modal selection fusion, efficiently integrating information from diverse modalities such as text semantics, pinyin, and glyphs. The model dynamically adjusts the significance of different types of information to prioritize features that most impact the correction outcomes. This approach enhances the model's flexibility and efficiency in processing information, ensuring consistent high performance across various complex scenarios.

(3) Residual connections are employed to fine-tune the original text vector, addressing potential issues such as gradient vanishing or exploding during training. This ensures that the deep network structure retains stable learning efficiency. Additionally, these connections enhance the model's generalization capability and improve both its accuracy and adaptability. By maintaining the integrity of the input information, the model avoids the loss of information during multi-layer processing, thereby enhancing the overall quality of error correction.

1 Related Work

The earliest approaches to Chinese spelling correction were rule-based and statistical methods. These methods relied on predefined rules and linguistic knowledge to identify and correct errors. Rule-based systems, such as those proposed by Chang and colleagues^[10], leveraged dictionaries and grammar rules to detect inconsistencies. However, these systems were limited by their reliance on exhaustive rule sets and struggled with context-sensitive errors.

Statistical methods emerged as an alternative, utilizing language models and statistical analysis to predict likely corrections. For example, Liu et al.^[11] employed n-gram models to estimate the probability of character sequences, thereby identifying unlikely or incorrect sequences. Despite their success in specific scenarios, these methods were constrained by the availability of large annotated corpora and the difficulty of capturing context in probabilistic models.

The advent of machine learning brought significant advancements to CSC. Supervised learning techniques, particularly those utilizing Support Vector Machines (SVMs) and Conditional Random Fields (CRFs), became popular. These models could learn patterns from labeled data and were more adaptable to various error types. The work of Zhang et al.^[12] demonstrated the effectiveness of CRFs in sequence labeling tasks, which are crucial for identifying and correcting spelling errors in context.

Deep learning, particularly with the introduction of neural networks, revolutionized CSC. Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) and their variants, such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, provided a means to capture long-range dependencies in text. Xie et al.^[13] demonstrated that neural network-based models significantly outperform traditional methods, particularly in handling complex sentence structures and context-sensitive errors. Wang et al.^[14] treated the CSC task as a sequence labeling problem and utilized bi-directional LSTM to predict correct characters.

The advent of transformer models, particularly BERT, brought a new era to CSC. BERT utilizes a deep bidirectional approach, enabling the model to consider the context from both the left and right of a token, which is crucial for understanding the nuances of language. In CSC, BERT has been used to enhance the detection and correction of spelling errors by leveraging its ability to understand context and semantics at a deeper level. Zhu et al.^[15] propose a novel general detector-corrector multi-task framework where the corrector uses BERT to capture the visual and phonological features from each character in the raw sentence and uses a late fusion strategy to fuse the hidden states of the corrector with that of the detector to minimize the negative impact from the misspelled characters. Zhang et al.^[16] propose a neural architecture consisting of two interconnected networks: one for error detection and another for error correction, both based on BERT. The detection network is connected to the correction network by Soft-Masking technique. This design allows the BERT model in the Correction Network to effectively utilize both local and global context information for spelling error correction. However, this model only employs the semantics of

BERT for error correction, which may limit its robustness.

Recent research has focused on leveraging multimodal information to enhance CSC. These approaches incorporate not only textual semantics but also phonetic (pinyin) and glyph (visual) information. The use of pinyin helps address phonetic errors, while glyph information aids in distinguishing visually similar characters. For example, the work of Zhang et al.^[17] utilized convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to extract glyph features and combined them with LSTM-based pinyin features, achieving state-of-the-art performance. The introduction of multi-head attention mechanisms, as seen in the work by Liu et al.^[18], further advanced multimodal CSC. These mechanisms allow models to focus on relevant aspects of each modality, dynamically adjusting their importance during error correction. This approach has proven particularly effective in handling the diverse types of errors present in Chinese text. Xu et al.^[19] proposed a selective fusion of three modalities using

a gating system. This method however has a potential disadvantage that it might lead to an over-reliance or over-fitting on pinyin information, consequently reducing the role of semantic information in the correction process. While multimodal approaches in CSC offer enhanced capabilities by leveraging multiple data sources, they also face challenges with data quality.

2 Model Description

In this section, we present the model and its specific implementation. Fig.1 illustrates the detailed framework of the model, which follows the principles of pretraining and fine-tuning. Spelling, semantic, and glyph encoders are employed to capture information from acoustic, textual, and visual modalities, respectively. The multimodal fusion module utilizes an attention mechanism to dynamically integrate information from these three encoders.

Fig.1 The overall framework of the model

As shown in Fig.1, the example input demonstrates the correction process for the incorrect character "字". To accurately correct this, the model leverages not only the surrounding textual context but also

the pinyin and glyph information specific to the character itself. Additionally, the process includes a residual concatenation of the original vectors, which helps refine the correction and accurately identify the correct character "学".

2.1 Pinyin Encoder

Pinyin is used in the Chinese language to represent the pronunciation of characters. It consists of three parts: consonants, rhymes, and tones. The vowels and rhymes are represented using English letters, while the tones $\{\bar{a}, \acute{a}, \check{a}, \grave{a}, \alpha\}$ are denoted by the numbers $\{1,2,3,4,0\}$. In this paper, we use Python's pinyin toolkit to convert Chinese characters to pinyin; for example, "好" is converted to "hao3". To model the phonological relationship between characters, the letters of each character's pinyin are first input into a layer of a unidirectional single-layer GRU network. The implementation of this process is described by the following formula.

$$\mathbf{h}_{i,j}^p = GRU(h_{i,j-1}^p, Emb(p_{i,j})) \quad (1)$$

where: $\mathbf{h}_{i,j}^p$ is the j th hidden state of the i th character as the output of the GRU, $Emb(p_{i,j})$ denotes the embedding of the pinyin letter $p_{i,j}$, and the last hidden state is used to make a character-level phonetic representation.

To enhance the model's ability to better understand the pinyin differences between Chinese characters and to obtain more contextual information, the character-level phonetic representation $\mathbf{H}_i^p = (h_1^p, \dots, h_N^p)$, previously obtained by the GRU, is applied to a Transformer to compute the pinyin contextual information. The formula is as follows.

$$\mathbf{H}_j^p = Transformer(\mathbf{H}_{j-1}^p), j \in [1,4] \quad (2)$$

where: \mathbf{H}_j^p is the pinyin representation obtained through j layers of a Transformer, and j is the number of Transformer layers. Each Transformer layer consists of a multi-head attention layer, a feedforward fully connected layer with residual connections and a normalization layer. In this paper, the output of the final layer is used as the final encoding of the pinyin modality:

$$\mathbf{H}^p = \mathbf{H}_j^p = (h_1^p, \dots, h_N^p) \quad (3)$$

2.2 Semantic Encoder

The main part of the semantic encoder in this paper consists of 12 Transformer blocks, which build upon the architecture used in BERT (base). Specifically, each Transformer layer has 768 hidden units

and 12 attention heads. This paper maps the input information $\mathbf{X} = (x_0, \dots, x_N)$ into $\mathbf{H}_i^s = (h_1^s, \dots, h_N^s)$ through word embedding, and then the Transformer processes the mapped word vectors to calculate a more accurate and comprehensive semantic representation. The formula is as follows.

$$\mathbf{H}_j^s = Transformer(\mathbf{H}_{j-1}^s), j \in [1,12] \quad (4)$$

where: \mathbf{H}_j^s is the contextual semantic representation obtained through the j -layer Transformer, and the output of the last layer is used as the final encoding of the semantic modality:

$$\mathbf{H}^s = \mathbf{H}_j^s = (h_1^s, \dots, h_N^s) \quad (5)$$

2.3 Glyph Encoder

Chinese characters, traditionally composed of strokes, can also be effectively represented using glyph images. Inspired by Sehanobish et al. [20] who used Chinese characters for Chinese entity recognition, this paper employs ResNet as a glyph encoder to extract glyph information. The glyph encoder consists of 6 ResNet blocks and includes a normalization layer. The input information $\mathbf{X} = (x_0, \dots, x_N)$ is converted into a glyph image $\mathbf{G}_i^g = (g_1^g, \dots, g_N^g)$ with a pixel size 64×64 using Python's pillow package. The formulas are as follows.

$$\mathbf{G}_j^g = ResNet_j(\mathbf{G}_{j-1}^g), j \in [1,6] \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{H}^g = Nomalize(\mathbf{G}_6^g) \quad (7)$$

where: j is the total number of blocks of ResNet, with the output $\mathbf{H}^g = (h_1^g, \dots, h_N^g)$ from the final normalization layer as the encoded glyph information.

To efficiently extract the glyph information, the size of the glyph image is gradually reduced through each processing layer while increasing the number of channels. This process results in a final output vector whose length equals the number of output channels, with the height and width of the image compressed to a single pixel. Additionally, the number of output channels is set to match the size of the hidden states of the semantic and pinyin encoders, facilitating the subsequent modal fusion process.

2.4 Multi-attention Fusion

To predict the final correct Chinese character, a

multi-head attention fusion module is developed to integrate vectors from different modalities. The vectors H^P , H^S and H^G representing pinyin, semantic, and glyph modalities respectively, are obtained using the encoders described above. To address integration challenges, this paper proposes a fusion module based on a bidirectional multi-head cross-attention mechanism. The multimodal fusion module consists of three components: Pinyin Attention, Semantic Attention, and Glyph Attention. While these components share the same structural model, they differ in their specific implementations of the query, key, and value parameters. Each component is designed to integrate information from one modality with from the other two, thereby computing a comprehensive representation for that modality.

Fig.2 Pinyin Modal Component

As exemplified by the pinyin modal component in Fig.2, each of the six layers is computed through a three-stage approach to effectively combine textual modalities with audio and visual cues. The method also utilizes prior and subsequent con-texts with residual connectivity in the computation of attention distributions.

(1) The cross-modal correlation and mapping relationship between the pinyin and semantic modalities are learned through a two-way multi-headed cross-attention operation. In this process, the pinyin modal information H^P is used as the Query, while the semantic modal information H^S serves as both

the Key and the Value.

$$\begin{aligned} [Q_m^{ps^j}, K_m^{ps^j}, V_m^{ps^j}] = \\ [F^{p^{j-1}} W Q_m^{ps^j}, H^S W K_m^{ps^j}, H^S W V_m^{ps^j}] \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} A_m^{ps^j} = \\ \text{Softmax} \left(\frac{Q_m^{ps^j} K_m^{ps^j T}}{\sqrt{d_{K_m^{ps^j}}}} \right) V_m^{ps^j}, m \in [1, M] \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MultiHead}^{ps^j} = \\ \text{Concat} (A_1^{ps^j}, \dots, A_M^{ps^j}) W^{Ops^j} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} F^{ps^j} = \\ \text{Nomalize} (F^{p^{j-1}} + \text{MultiHead}^{ps^j}) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where: j is the number of model layers, the initial pinyin modal information is denoted as $F^{p^{j-1}} = (f_1^{p^{j-1}}, \dots, f_N^{p^{j-1}})$, when $j=1$, $F^{p^0} = H^P$. Let m be the number of heads in the multi-head attention mechanism,

The matrices $W Q_m^{ps^j}$, $W K_m^{ps^j}$, $W V_m^{ps^j}$, W^{Ops^j} are the trainable parameter matrices. $A_m^{ps^j}$ signifies the attentional weights of the pinyin and semantic modalities, MultiHead^{ps^j} reflects the multi-head attentional outputs of the pinyin and semantic modalities, and F^{ps^j} is the first-stage outputs derived from the normalization layer and residual connections.

(2) The output F^{ps^j} learned in the first stage is then used as a new Query, while the glyph modality is treated as the Key and the Value in another bi-directional multi-headed cross-attention layer. This layer merges the pinyin modality and glyph modalities.

$$\begin{aligned} [Q_m^{psg^j}, K_m^{psg^j}, V_m^{psg^j}] = \\ [F^{ps^j} W Q_m^{psg^j}, H^G W K_m^{psg^j}, H^G W V_m^{psg^j}] \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$\begin{aligned} A_m^{psg^j} = \\ \text{Softmax} \left(\frac{Q_m^{psg^j} K_m^{psg^j T}}{\sqrt{d_{K_m^{psg^j}}}} \right) V_m^{psg^j}, m \in [1, M] \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MultiHead}^{psg^j} = \\ \text{Concat} (A_1^{psg^j}, \dots, A_M^{psg^j}) W^{Opsg^j} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

$$\begin{aligned} F^{psg^j} = \\ \text{Nomalize} (F^{ps^j} + \text{MultiHead}^{psg^j}) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Here, $W_m^{psg^j}$, $W_m^{Kpsg^j}$, $W_m^{Vpsg^j}$, $W_m^{Opsg^j}$ are the trainable parameter matrices, $A_m^{psg^j}$ represents the attentional weights of the three modalities, **MultiHead** $^{psg^j}$ is the multi-head attentional output of the three modalities, and F^{psg^j} is the second-stage output derived from the normalization layer and residual connection.

(3) To enhance the model, a feed-forward fully connected network layer and a normalization layer are added.

$$FFN^{p^j} = \max(0, F^{psg^j} W_1^{p^j} + b_1^{p^j}) W_2^{p^j} + b_2^{p^j} \quad (16)$$

$$F^{p^j} = \text{Normalize}(F^{psg^j} + FFN^{p^j}) \quad (17)$$

where: $W_1^{p^j}$, $b_1^{p^j}$, $W_2^{p^j}$, $b_2^{p^j}$ are trainable parameter matrices and bias vectors, and $\max()$ is the ReLU activation function. After the three modal components are fused to calculate F^p , F^s , and F^g respectively, they are summed up to obtain the final multimodal feature representation $F = (f_1, \dots, f_N)$.

$$F = F^p + F^s + F^g \quad (18)$$

2.5 Residual Connection

To prevent issues such as gradient dissipation and gradient explosion caused by in-creasing network depth, this model introduces residual connections and incorporates a classification layer consisting of three Transformer layers and a Softmax layer. The output vector is calculated using residual connections with the original input vector.

$$F_0 = F + \text{Emb}(x_i) \quad (19)$$

$$F_j = \text{Transformer}(F_{j-1}), j \in [1,3] \quad (20)$$

$$y_i = \text{Softmax}(f_i W_3 + b_3), f_i \in F_3 \quad (22)$$

where: x_i is the original input vector, F denotes the multimodal feature information, and y_i represents the probability that the i th character is predicted correctly. The parameters W_3 , b_3 are the trainable parameter matrix and bias vector, respectively.

In summary, our model offers several key advantages in feature extraction and architectural design.

(1) **Holistic Representation:** By integrating phonetic, glyph, and semantic features, the model gains a comprehensive view of each Chinese character and its usage. This reduces confusion arising from

homophones, visually similar characters, and context-dependent errors.

(2) **Enhanced Contextual Understanding:** Multi-head attention ensures the model can simultaneously focus on different aspects of the context, improving its ability to pinpoint and correct errors arising from various sources.

(3) **Stable and Effective Training:** Residual connections help maintain crucial information across layers and support deeper architectures, making the model more robust and easier to fine-tune on specialized datasets.

3 Experiment

In this section, the datasets involved in the study and the settings used for training and testing our model are first introduced. Next, a detailed overview of the experimental results is provided, followed by quantitative and qualitative comparisons between the proposed model and state-of-the-art methods. Finally, the effectiveness of the proposed model is verified through ablation studies and in-depth analysis.

3.1 Data Set

To ensure a fair comparison with previous models, this paper uses SIGHAN training data along with the 271K pseudo-data generated by Wang et al.^[14] as the training set. The performance is evaluated on three SIGHAN datasets (SIGHAN13, SIGHAN14, SIGHAN15). Initially, the SIGHAN datasets were in Traditional Chinese; we use the OpenCC tool^[21] to convert the data to Simplified Chinese and remove some mislabeled data from the SIGHAN14 and SIGHAN15 training sets. Due to the relatively poor quality of annotations in the SIGHAN13 test set, which adversely affected test performance, we corrected specific inaccuracies such as the mislabeling of "的", "地" and "得" within the dataset. Following these corrections, the models were evaluated to assess improvements in performance.

3.2 Experimental Parameter Settings and Evaluation Metrics

Our model is developed using Python 3.8 and the deep learning framework PyTorch, version 1.10.0. Comparative experiments with other baseline models

are conducted within the same environment to ensure consistency. We employ the pretrained weights from the BERT-wwm model^[22] to initialize the semantic encoder instead of training it from scratch. The embedding and hidden layer dimensions are standardized at 768 for all modalities. The learning rate is set to 5e-5, and the batch size is configured to 16.

For evaluating the experiments, we combine two levels of precision (P), recall (R) and F1 score as performance metrics. At the detection level, a sentence is considered correct only when all spelling errors in the sentence are successfully detected. At the correction level, the model must not only detect the wrong characters but also correct all of them accurately.

3.3 Pre-training

To enhance the pinyin and glyph encoding modules' ability to learn the relationships between acoustic-text and visual-text, we pre-train these two modules. For pinyin encoding, a linear layer is added on top of the encoder to convert the output hidden state into a probability distribution over the Chinese character vocabulary. The speech encoder is pre-trained with the pinyin sequences of sentences containing spelling errors in the training data, aiming to restore the correct character sequences.

For glyph encoding, a linear layer is also added for classification purposes. Given a Chinese character image, the glyph encoder learns the feature information and predicts the corresponding character from the Chinese character vocabulary.

Finally, the pretrained weights of the semantic encoder, pinyin encoder, and glyph encoder are loaded, and the CSC training data is used for the final training process.

3.4 Baselines

In this section, models that have demonstrated effectiveness in the Chinese spelling correction task (CSC) task in recent years are selected for comparison:

- BERT^[3]: The BERT (base) model.
- SpellGCN^[23]: This model integrates a Graph Convolutional Network with BERT to learn the structural

relationship between word sounds and shapes. It incorporates vectors of word sounds and shapes into the word embeddings, followed by error correction in the correction module.

- Realise^[19]: This model uses specific semantic, speech, and graphic encoders to capture various forms of information. A selective modal fusion mechanism is proposed to control the flow of information from these modalities, merging and correcting errors.
- MDCSpell^[15]: This approach designs a multimodal framework where BERT serves as a corrector to capture the visual and phonetic features of the input information. It also integrates the hidden state of the detector to minimize the impact of errors.
- LEAD^[24]: The model constructs positive and negative samples based on the knowledge of Chinese character phonology, glyphs and definitions from the dictionary. A unified contrastive learning training scheme is then used to refine the representation of the CSC model.
- DORM^[25]: The model separates the features of textual and speech information, enabling direct interaction between the two modalities. To mitigate the risk of overfitting to speech data, the authors introduced a self-distillation module, ensuring that semantic information remains the primary driver of predictions.

3.5 Experimental Results

Table 2 shows the evaluation scores of our model alongside other baseline models on the SIGHAN13/14/15 test sets at both the detection and correction levels. The metrics include Precision (P_d), Recall (R_d) and F1 score (F_{1d}) for detection, as well as Precision (P_c), Recall (R_c) and F1 score (F_{1c}) for correction.

The model significantly outperforms the baseline models across all test sets. Specifically, on SIGHAN15, the Detection F1 scores, and Correction F1 scores improve by 11.2% 10%, respectively, over BERT.

Compared to other BERT extensions, this model's use of multimodal information for Chinese characters proves more advantageous.

On SIGHAN15, the Detection F1 scores and Correction F1 scores improve by 9.8% and 9.2% over

SpellGCN.

Although SpellGCN also utilizes multimodal information, it relies on a specific con-fusion set, making the model less capable of generalization.

Compared to Realise and MDCSpell, our model demonstrates superior performance across the three SIGHAN test sets, with corrected F1 scores improving by 0.6%, 2.9%, and 1.4% on SIGHAN13,

SIGHAN14, SIGHAN15, respectively. Additionally, on SIGHAN15, the model achieves detection and correction F1 scores that are 0.5% and 0.1% higher, respectively, than those of DORM.

However, it is noted that our model is not optimal in terms of recall, potentially due to failures in correctly identifying or correcting erroneous characters within sentences.

Table 2 Quantitative comparison with other baseline models, with the best results are in bold.

Dataset	Model	P_d	R_d	F_{1d}	P_c	R_c	F_{1c}
SIGHAN13	BERT	79.0	72.8	75.8	77.7	71.6	74.6
	SpellGCN	80.1	74.4	77.2	78.3	72.7	75.4
	Realise	88.6	82.5	85.4	87.2	81.2	84.1
	MDCSpell	89.1	78.3	83.4	87.5	76.8	81.8
	LEAD	88.3	83.4	85.8	87.2	82.4	84.7
	DORM	87.9	83.7	85.8	86.8	82.7	84.7
	Our model	93.4	81.4	87.0	89.3	80.7	84.8
SIGHAN14	BERT	64.5	68.6	66.5	62.4	66.3	64.3
	SpellGCN	65.1	69.5	67.2	63.1	67.2	65.3
	Realise	67.8	71.5	69.6	66.3	70.0	68.1
	MDCSpell	70.2	68.8	69.5	69.0	67.7	68.3
	LEAD	70.7	71.0	70.8	69.3	69.6	69.5
	DORM	69.5	73.1	71.2	68.4	71.9	70.1
	Our model	73.3	71.1	72.1	72.4	69.5	70.9
SIGHAN15	BERT	74.2	78.0	76.1	71.6	75.3	73.4
	SpellGCN	74.8	80.7	77.7	72.1	77.7	75.9
	Realise	77.3	81.3	79.3	75.9	79.9	77.8
	MDCSpell	80.8	80.6	80.7	78.4	78.2	78.3
	LEAD	79.2	82.8	80.9	77.6	81.2	79.3
	DORM	77.9	84.3	81.0	76.6	82.8	79.6
	Our model	83.2	79.8	81.5	81.1	78.4	79.7

3.6 Cross-Domain Evaluation

To assess the generalization ability of our model in specialized domains, we conducted evaluations using the ECSpell^[26] benchmark. This benchmark includes corpora from three distinct professional domains: legal (LAW), medical (MED), and official documents (ODW). The LAW corpus consists of 1,960 training examples and 500 test examples, the MED corpus includes 3,000 training examples and

500 test examples, and the ODW corpus contains 1,728 training examples and 500 test examples. To adapt our model to these domain-specific tasks, we applied the Masked-FT (MFT) technique, a simple yet effective fine-tuning method that uniformly masks non-error characters in the source sentences.

By analyzing the results presented in Table 2 and Table 3, we observe that the performance of the original model decreases significantly when transferred to domain-specific tasks, highlighting the

challenges of adapting general error correction models to specialized fields. However, compared to the baseline models, our proposed model demonstrates superior performance across all three domains, achieving higher F1 scores.

While this paper primarily focuses on general error correction, the results highlight our model's ability to adapt to specialized domains. Its performance across all three professional fields demonstrates robustness and versatility, making it a promising option for broader applications.

Table 3 Comparison of F1 scores with other baseline models on the ECSpell benchmark

Model	LAW	MED	ODW
BERT	40.2	26.9	26.7
BERT-MFT	76.8	63.8	62.9
MDCSpell	42.2	25.7	27.5
MDCSpell-MFT	81.1	72.4	72
Our model	62.3	43.4	47.4
Our model-MFT	82.3	79.1	75.2

4 Model Analysis

4.1 Ablation Study

To further analyze the performance impact of each component, ablation experiments were conducted.

(1) removing the pinyin encoding module and using only semantic and grapheme encoding;

(2) removing the grapheme encoding module and using only semantic and pinyin encoding;

(3) removing the multi-attention fusion module and using standard summation fusion;

(4) removing residual fine-tuning;

(5) removing pre-training for both the pinyin and grapheme encoding modules.

As reported in Table 3, the F1 scores for detection and correction resulting from removal of different modules on the SIGHAN15 test set are shown. The primary motivation of this study is to identify similar relationships between characters by combining pinyin and glyph encoders.

Table 3 Results of ablation experiments, where “w/o” means “without”, “PE” denotes the pinyin embedding, “GE” stands for the graphic embedding, “AF” indicates the multi-head attention fusion, and “RC” represents the residual connection.

Method	F_{1d}	F_{1c}
Our model	81.5	79.7
w/o PE	79.3	78.4
w/o GE	80.1	78.7
w/o AF	78.2	76.8
w/o RC	80.8	79.2
w/o pre-train	80.5	78.9

The data in Table 3 indicates a decline of 2.2% and 1.3% in detection F1 scores, and 1.4% and 1.0% in correction F1 scores, when the pinyin or glyph encoder is removed, respectively. The greater performance degradation when removing the pinyin encoder compared to the glyph encoder suggests that pinyin features are more critical for Chinese spelling error correction. Additionally, substituting the multi-head attention fusion with standard summation fusion results in decreases of 3.3% and 2.9% in detection and correction F1 scores, respectively, highlighting the superior capability of the attention mechanism to effectively utilize multimodal information and enhance model precision. The removal of residual connections led to reductions of 0.7% and 0.5% in F1 scores, suggesting that residual fine-tuning can further refine the results and improve precision. The elimination of pretraining caused a decrease in F1 scores by 1.0% and 0.8%.

Fig.3 shows that removing multi-head attention fusion has the most significant impact on performance degradation, indicating that better integration of multimodal information is the key to improving performance. The performance degradation, regardless of which component is removed, strongly testifies to the validity and importance of each part of the model.

Fig.3 Results of Component Removal on Detection and Correction F1 Scores

4.2 Case Analysis

Further examples are provided to demonstrate our model's superior performance. Fig.4 exhibits the results of different models for correcting the input statements, with incorrect characters underlined and their corrections shown in brackets. In the first example, "的" is the error character in the input statement. The Soft-Masked BERT model does not consider pinyin similarity and suggests "英" as a correction, whereas our model correctly changes the error character to "德" based on pinyin similarity.

In the second example, "旅" is the wrong character in the input statement. SpellGCN cannot correct this because it relies on a predefined confusion set that does not include "旅" and "游". However, our model considers the glyph similarity and correctly changes "旅" to "游" by recognizing their similar glyph structures. In the third example, "帅" is the error character in the input statement. Although the Realise model adaptively combines pinyin, glyph, and semantic information, it incorrectly prioritizes glyph information due to visual similarity, resulting in the incorrect correction to "师". In contrast, our model accurately changes “帅” to "室", effectively using the contextual information to guide the correction process.

Input	Output
你的(德)语说的真好	Soft-Masked BERT: 你 <u>英</u> 语说的真好
	Our model: 你 <u>德</u> 语说的真好
昨天有人上街 <u>旅</u> (游)行	SpellGCN: 昨天有人上街 <u>旅</u> 行
	Our model: 昨天有人上街 <u>游</u> 行
教 <u>帅</u> (室)很安静	Realise: 教 <u>师</u> 很安静
	Our model: 教 <u>室</u> 很安静

Fig.4 Case analysis, where misspellings are highlighted in red, and the correct characters are shown in parentheses

4.3 Error Analysis

This section delves into the analysis of errors occurring in the models on the test dataset, identifying three prevalent types of errors.

As shown in Fig.5, one type of error is continuous misspellings, where multiple characters are incorrect consecutively. For instance, in the phrase "玉笛落在屋檐上" ("玉笛" should be "雨滴"), the model has low precision for this type of error because the overall sentence semantics cause interference.

The second type of error involves technical terms. An example is the phrase "幽门罗杆菌感染可能影响胃部," where "罗" is incorrect and should be "螺" in "幽门螺杆菌". These errors often remain uncorrected because the model lacks training on specialized datasets relevant to specific technical vocabularies.

The third type of error is found in literary poetry. For example, in the phrase "闻道有前后，术业有专攻", where "前" is incorrect, the model fails to correct it to "先" because the semantics are still reasonable.

Each error type highlights specific limitations in the current modeling approach, underscoring the need for more sophisticated handling of context, specialized terminology, and continuous error patterns in language models.

Error Type	Input	Output
Continuous errors	玉 <u>笛</u> (雨滴) 落在屋檐上	玉 <u>笛</u> 落在屋檐上
Technical terms errors	幽 <u>门罗</u> (螺) 杆菌感染可能影响胃部	幽 <u>门螺</u> 杆菌感染可能影响胃部
Literary poetry errors	闻道有 <u>前</u> (先) 后，术业有专攻	闻道有 <u>先</u> 后，术业有专攻

Fig.5 Error analysis cases, where misspellings are highlighted in red, with the correct characters are shown in parentheses

5 Conclusion

This study proposes a method of fusing pinyin, semantic, and glyph feature information through multi-head attention, combined with a Transformer-based classification layer for error correction. Given that Chinese spelling errors often closely resemble correct characters in terms of pinyin, semantics, and glyphs, this approach effectively leverages information from textual, acoustic, and visual modalities to detect and correct errors. Additionally, a dy-

dynamic fusion mechanism based on multi-head attention is introduced to integrate the feature information from these modalities. Experiments on the SIGHAN benchmark test demonstrate that the proposed model outperforms other benchmark models, showing superior error detection and correction capabilities.

In future research, a key focus should be on exploring the integration of additional modalities, such as contextual or syntactic information, to further enhance the model's performance. Another avenue for improvement is developing more advanced techniques to dynamically balance the contribution of each modality based on the specific context of the text. Additionally, refining the model to better handle rare and domain-specific terms, as well as continuous error patterns, will be crucial. Reducing false positives in both detection and correction will also be an important area of focus, ensuring that the model not only corrects errors more accurately but also avoids unnecessary alterations to the text.

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